

SOME MICROBIOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF HYDROPONICS

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Background

Aquaponics: The operating principle of the system is briefly as follows: the organic and inorganic decomposition products generated during the feeding and growth of the fish are eliminated by passing them through a root zone hydroponic system, and then the purified water is returned to the fish. Although the system sounds simple, it is based on very complex, multi-stage microbiological foundations. Our aim was to investigate this complex system focusing on ammonia oxidising microbes.

Material and methods:

The samples came from a stable aquaponics system in which we cultivated carp and lettuce. DNS preparation: Mo Bio PowerSoil® DNA Isolation kit; PCR: DreamTaq (Fermentas) polimerase, PTC 200 Thermalcycler; qPCR: Maxima SYBR Green qPCR Master Mix, Bioer Line-Gene K.

Results:

An effective method for studying complex microbial systems from aquaponics

FT: fish tank
P: plant cultivation

The pattern of the fish tank and the plant part after four weeks of continuous feeding and recirculation by using high protein feed (50%)

Effect:

A) Appearance of cellulose-degrading bacteria in the growing part of the plant
B) Appearance of ammonia oxidizers

C: Cellulose degrading bacteria
FT: Fish Tank
P: Plant

The pattern of the fish tank and the plant part after four weeks of continuous feeding and recirculation by using low protein feed (5%)

Effect:

A) Appearance of pectinase-degrading bacteria in the growing part of the plant

PE: Pectin degrading Bacteria
FT: Fish Tank
P: Plant

Summary:

We investigated the microbial composition of an aquaponic system, which required optimizing detection methods. As a result of the successful development, we were able to detect ammonia oxidizers, cellulose and pectin decomposers, and their changes depending on feeding.

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